

Amnesic Pathologies in Regulation of Dopamine as Supplement to Wernicke-Korsakoff Syndrome: A Limbic-Reticular Coupling View

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Abstract

Background: It was suggested by the limbic-reticular coupling theory that the hippocampus and amygdala regulate such descending limbic structures as the mammillary bodies, septum, hypothalamus and habenula, and in turn regulate the ascending noradrenergic, serotonergic, dopaminergic and cholinergic systems to consolidate and recall declarative memory, while the anterior and mediodorsal thalamic nuclei of Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome beyond limbic-reticular coupling be related else to familiarity. **Aim:** It was aimed to highlight a portion of limbic-reticular coupling structures in alcoholic Korsakoff's syndrome, including the dopaminergic system, habenula, mammillary bodies, etc. **Methods:** It was searched the papers from Pubmed and Baidu. **Results and Discussions:** It is highlighted that, (a) the mesolimbic dopamine, liable to be affected by alcohol, induces the hippocampal theta rhythm via septum, helping encode and consolidate new memories, such as dopaminergic enhancement of motivational declarative memory in young human adults; (b) dopamine can activate cortical gamma wave and help recall; (c) joint damage of habenula and mammillary bodies, both sending efferents to ventral tegmental area(VTA) rich in dopaminergic neurons, is sufficient to cause Korsakoff's amnesia; (d) the loop of hippocampal CA3 to lateral septum(LS) to VTA(CA3-LS-VTA) activates dopamine for contextual memory in animals, consistent with dopaminergic antagonist impairing declarative memory recall in humans; (e) whereas thiamine deficiency, the major nutritional deficit causing Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome, impairs noradrenergic but spares dopaminergic system. **Conclusion:** It is supplemented the integrative dysfunctions in regulation of such neglected dopaminergic system, including the habenula, mammillary bodies and VTA dopamine, as partial contribution to memory impairments in Korsakoff's syndrome.

Introduction

Extensive studies have been performed on alcoholic Korsakoff's syndrome, and there are many reviews on this issue [1-3]. The contemporary trend combines the Korsakoff's syndrome and Wernicke's encephalopathy into Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome as both resulting from thiamine deficiency, with the Korsakoff's syndrome developing as residue of Wernicke's encephalopathy not recovering well in time [1-2]. Chronic alcoholic intake is one of the important causes resulting in thiamine deficiency [1-3], and is also considered as one of the important factors facilitating the progression of Wernicke's syndrome to Korsakoff's syndrome [1-2].

Amnesia is often adopted to distinguish Wernicke's syndrome and Korsakoff's syndrome. Amnesia is the salient clinical manifestation of Korsakoff's disease [1-3], while it is not an indispensable representation and is sometimes even spared in nonalcoholic Wernicke's encephalopathy[2,4]. Obviously, it is interesting to reveal the amnesic causes of Korsakoff's disease to distinguish it from Wernicke's encephalopathy. The brain structures disrupted in Korsakoff's disease mainly involve the diencephalic structures, including the periventricular structures, mammillary bodies, thalamic nuclei, cerebellum and so on[1-3,5]. These disrupted diencephalic structures in Korsakoff's disease

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provide important clues to reveal the pathological causes of amnesia in the disease.

Related Theories on Amnesia

Researches in amnesia have been integrated to generate several theories for neural circuits in brain to process memory. The amnesia in Korsakoff's disease can benefit from the theoretical brain circuits on memory to reveal the relevant structures responsible for producing the memory impairments in this syndrome.

The disconnection theory proposed by Warrington and Weiskrantz suggested that the memory impairment resulting from the disrupted diencephalic structures, such as the mammillary bodies, anterior and mediodorsal thalamic nuclei, be due to the damage to these diencephalic structures connecting the memory storage site in temporal lobe to the complex cognition site in prefrontal and cingulate cortex[6]. The mammillary bodies, anterior and mediodorsal thalamic nuclei important for connection of these memory processing sites in this theory are frequently destroyed in Korsakoff's disease[1-3,5].

The limbic-reticular coupling theory of Cai proposed that the hippocampus and amygdala regulate such descending limbic structures as the mammillary bodies, septum, hypothalamus, stria medullaris and habenula, and in turn regulate the ascending noradrenergic, serotonergic, dopaminergic and cholinergic systems, thereby accomplish declarative memory consolidation and recall[7]. The mammillary bodies, periventricular stria medullaris and habenula important for processing memory in this theory are frequently destroyed in Korsakoff's disease[2,5]. Meanwhile, the limbic-reticular coupling theory suggested that the lesions to anterior and mediodorsal thalamic nuclei impair transfer of memory stored in temporal lobe to prefrontal and cingulate cortex for feeling of familiarity of the memory, different from memory consolidation and recall[7].

For these two theories, it is consensus that the anterior and mediodorsal thalamic nuclei relay memory storage in temporal lobe to memory cognition or familiarity in prefrontal and cingulate cortex. Their contributions to the amnesia of Korsakoff's disease would as well be considered as consistent between the two theories. However, how the limbic-reticular coupling pathways, for memory consolidation and recall, different from the anterior and mediodorsal thalamic nuclei, are involved in Korsakoff's disease is not clear, and is required for further consideration. In this article, it is mainly focused on the consideration of these limbic-reticular coupling structures to Korsakoff's amnesia.

Methods

For this complex and interdisciplinary subject, the integrative review of progressions in related subfields was the best and most convincing method. Meta-

analysis fit investigation of a specific topic in a well-studied subfield, while neglected many discussions in various review papers. Besides, it was certainly more important to analyze and integrate the collected reviews and new research papers from several fields by classification, comparison and summarization.

Paper search was mainly performed on Pubmed and Baidu Xueshu. The first preference was given to relevant updated reviews. If there was no appropriate updated review, then the relevant reviews published at more than 10 years ago were allowed for citation. If there was neither appropriate old review, then the research articles with repeated experimental results were collected for citation.

Results and Discussions

Dopamine, Alcohol and Memory

Alcohol intake and dopamine

Alcohol intake is usually the most common cause gradually leading to Korsakoff's disease[1,3]. Biochemical and pharmacological studies are most accurate and convincing to reveal the brain targets of ethanol effects. These studies have demonstrated that acute administration of ethanol usually activates the mesolimbic dopamine system and releases dopamine[8-10]. In contrast, chronic exposure to ethanol results in functional reduction of the mesolimbic dopamine system[8-9]. The detailed underlying biochemical mechanisms are still under more investigations.

Dopamine and memory

Dopamine can influence new memory acquisition and consolidation, as well as memory recall, which are the two major concerns of limbic-reticular coupling theory. Herein it is considered these two issues one by one.

For new declarative memory acquisition and consolidation, in limbic-reticular coupling theory, the amygdala and hippocampal CA1 theta are considered as coordinating novelty attention and declarative memory consolidation[7]. In relevance, the ascending dopaminergic system in ventral tegmental area(VTA) enhances the hippocampal theta rhythm via septum[11-12]. In accordance, the dopaminergic enhancement of hippocampal theta may facilitate declarative memory [7]. In consistence by evidence, it has been reported that the young, but not old, adults of humans are significantly more likely to remember new words associated with motivational cues than neutral cues [13], supporting the dopaminergic regulated motivation in enhancement of new declarative memory acquisition and consolidation.

For declarative memory recall, in limbic-reticular coupling theory the dopaminergic system is thought as partial mediating recall along with the serotonergic and cholinergic systems [7]. In consistence by evidence, it has been reported that the dopaminergic antagonist

haloperidol can mildly impair declarative memory recall in humans[14].

In brief, available evidences suggest that dopamine can enhance new declarative memory acquisition, consolidation and recall in humans.

Dopaminergic effects on gamma and theta wave

The modulation of dopamine onto cortex is complicated, because dopamine can not only modulate both pyramidal neurons and several classes of interneurons[15-17], but also activate several different types of dopaminergic receptors in cortex[15,18]. Accordingly, it is necessary to consider the gross effects of dopamine on modulation of cortical activities.

Theta wave and gamma wave are widely studied as integrative cortical activities related to modulation of memory. In theta-gamma coupling of limbic-reticular coupling theory, the hippocampal theta wave activates the cholinergic neurons in basal forebrain, while the cholinergic neurons modulate gamma wave to recall declarative memories in cortex[7].

Enhancement of gamma wave has mostly been demonstrated as the effects by dopaminergic receptors in cortex[19-21]. Whether such dopaminergic enhancement of gamma wave can directly facilitate recall or accessorially assist recall requires more investigations. On the other hand, dopamine has sometimes been reported to reduce theta wave but increase delta wave[22-23], opposite to the VTA-dopamine's enhancement of hippocampal theta rhythm via septum[11-12]. Obviously, more investigations are required for further clarification of these complicated effects of dopamine.

Subcortical Limbic Regulation on Dopamine in VTA

Subcortical limbic afferents to VTA

The diencephalic structures disrupted in Korsakoff's disease mainly involve the periventricular structures, mammillary bodies, thalamic nuclei, cerebellum and so on[1-3,5], among which the periventricular habenula and mammillary bodies are within the limbic-reticular coupling pathways for declarative memory consolidation and recall[7].

Brain VTA rich in ascending dopaminergic neurons receives afferents from lateral habenula[24]. Meanwhile, the medial mammillary nucleus also sends efferents to VTA[25]. Accordingly, in anatomy, both habenula and mammillary bodies can modulate the neurons in VTA.

Loop of hippocampal CA3 to lateral septum to VTA

In 2011, a paper published in "Science" illustrated that stimulation of hippocampal CA3 neurons with theta frequency excited the dopaminergic neurons in VTA[26]. Later, it was likewise reported that the loop of hippocampal CA3 to lateral septum(LS) to VTA(CA3-LS-VTA) activated the dopaminergic neurons in VTA[27]. Obviously, the dopaminergic activation by CA3-LS-VTA

is one of the important components of limbic-reticular coupling for processing memories[7].

Either habenula or mammillary bodies may play intermediate roles in the CA3-LS-VTA loop. It has been reported that small damage to medial mammillary bodies might not necessarily cause memory impairment in human[28], while there has been no data available now regarding to whether small damage solely to habenula is sufficient to cause amnesia in humans. In limbic-reticular coupling theory, integrative or gross rather than individual coupling is emphasized, so should it here be considered both habenula and mammillary bodies as integrative or gross intermediators for CA3-LS-VTA loop.

Small diencephalic damages for amnesia

It is certainly interesting to find out the very small diencephalic damages to cause amnesia. Even though small damage restricted to medial mammillary bodies has been reported to spare memory in human[28], larger lesions around the mammillary bodies manifested impairments on free recall but not familiarity[29-31].

Joint damages only to both mammillary bodies and midline thalamus disconnecting habenula can be small, but have been repeatedly reported as sufficient to cause amnesia in humans. For instance, in Korsakoff's cases E.A. and H.J.[32] as well as J.W. and B.C.[33], the joint lesions were restricted only to mammillary bodies and a small region medial to the mediodorsal thalamic nucleus but not the mediodorsal nucleus itself, which might destroy the stria medullaris and habenula. Besides, it was even demonstrated in a comparative study that the anterograde amnesia in alcoholic Korsakoff's syndrome was associated with atrophy of the nuclei in the midline of the thalamus, but not with atrophy of the mammillary bodies, the hippocampus, or the parahippocampal gyrus[5].

Taken together from all these studies on mammillary bodies and midline thalamic structures related to habenula, it is herein summarized that damages to mammillary bodies and habenula can at least integratively or jointly contribute to memory impairments in Korsakoff's disease.

Dopaminergic Dysregulation Supplemental to Wernicke-Korsakoff Syndrome

Thiamine deficiency damaging noradrenaline but not dopamine

Many reviews consider thiamine deficiency as the major cause of Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome, with Korsakoff's syndrome developing as residue of Wernicke's encephalopathy not recovering well timely[1-2]. Obviously, it is necessary to investigate whether thiamine deficiency may damage the dopaminergic neurons in brain.

Unfortunately, available biochemical evidences up to now in rats have shown that thiamine deficiency

reduced norepinephrine in cortex and hippocampus, especially entorhinal cortex[34-35], while did not reduce other monoamines including dopamine and serotonin in forebrain[34-35].

Dopaminergic dysregulation supplemental to Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome

As demonstrated above, joint lesions restricted only to mammillary bodies and a small region in midline of the thalamus related to habenula were sufficient to cause amnesia in Korsakoff's syndrome[5,32-33]. Meanwhile, it was also demonstrated in anatomy that both habenula and mammillary bodies were able to modulate the neurons of VTA[24-25]. In accordance, the impaired function of mammillary bodies and habenula in Korsakoff's syndrome[5,32-33] would dysregulate the dopaminergic neurons in VTA, even though thiamine deficiency of Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome could only reduce norepinephrine but not dopamine in forebrain[34-35]. These are the amnesic pathologies in regulation of such neglected dopamine as supplement to Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome.

Habenula and control of alcohol intake

Some reviews have pointed out that pure thiamine deficiency unaccompanied by chronic and excessive consumption of alcohol manifested slow in rate of progression to Korsakoff's syndrome[4]. Obviously, control of alcohol intake should be considered as an important factor in causing Korsakoff's syndrome.

As demonstrated above, acute administration of ethanol usually activates the mesolimbic dopamine system and releases dopamine[8-10], while chronic exposure to ethanol reduces the function of mesolimbic dopamine system[8-9]. This is one aspect that associates dopamine with alcohol intake.

Habenula, able to regulate the dopaminergic neurons in VTA[24], is another brain structure involved in regulation of alcohol intake. It was demonstrated that downregulation of M-channels in lateral habenula mediated the hyperalgesia during alcohol withdrawal in rats[36], while the rats with lesions of the lateral habenula showed accelerated escalation of voluntary ethanol consumption[37]. With the midline thalamic structures related to habenula often destroyed in Korsakoff's syndrome[5,32-33], it would escalate the voluntary ethanol consumption in these patients.

Because alcohol intake is the most common cause of Korsakoff's disease[1-3], the regulation of alcohol intake by mesolimbic dopamine and habenula is certainly important to be considered for the progression of Korsakoff's disease in addition to thiamine deficiency.

Conclusion

Both disconnection theory and limbic-reticular coupling theory agreed that the anterior and mediodorsal thalamic nuclei relayed memory storage in temporal lobe to memory cognition or familiarity in prefrontal and cingulate cortex, while lesions of these thalamic nuclei were the important cause of amnesia in Korsakoff's syndrome. In this article, it is further considered some brain structures related to memory consolidation and recall in limbic-reticular coupling theory beyond these thalamic nuclei, and reviewed these additional limbic-reticular coupling structures in regulation of dopaminergic neurons in VTA to supplement the amnesic pathologies of Korsakoff's syndrome.

The dopaminergic neurons in VTA induce the hippocampal theta rhythm via septum, and help encode and consolidate new memories, such as dopaminergic enhancement of motivational declarative memory in young human adults. Besides, dopamine can activate cortical gamma wave and help recall, while shift theta wave to delta wave, in which its complicated roles on memory require further investigation.

The habenula and mammillary bodies, often destroyed in Korsakoff's syndrome, both send efferents to VTA and regulate dopaminergic activities. The CA3-LS-VTA loop activates dopamine for contextual memory in animals, consistent with dopaminergic antagonist impairing declarative memory recall in humans.

Thiamine deficiency, the major nutritional deficit causing Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome, impairs noradrenergic but spares dopaminergic system in animals. Also considering the roles of dopamine on memory, as well as the damage to habenula, mammillary bodies in Korsakoff's amnesia, it is supplemented these integrative brain dysfunctions in the habenula, mammillary bodies, and the neglected VTA dopamine as partial contribution to the memory impairments in Korsakoff's syndrome.

In parallel, since pure thiamine deficiency without chronic and excessive consumption of alcohol is slow in rate of progression to Korsakoff's syndrome, control of alcohol intake is an important factor for Korsakoff's syndrome. Both mesolimbic dopamine and habenula happen to be involved in regulation of alcohol intake, while disruption of them in Korsakoff's syndrome would escalate the voluntary ethanol consumption in these patients.

Table 1 outlines the amnesic pathologies in regulation of dopamine as supplement to Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome.

Table 1: Amnesic Pathologies in Regulation of Dopamine in Korsakoff's Syndrome

	Dopamine in ventral tegmental area	Mammillary bodies	Habenula
Thiamine deficiency	Thiamine deficiency spares dopamine, even though reduces noradrenaline.	Mammillary bodies are often destroyed in Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome deficient in thiamine.	Periventricular structures related to habenula are often destroyed in Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome deficient in thiamine.
Alcohol intake	Acute alcohol activates dopamine, while chronic and excessive consumption of alcohol reduces dopamine function, and facilitates the progression to Korsakoff's syndrome.	Chronic alcohol intake results in thiamine deficiency, and impairs the mammillary bodies in Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome.	Lateral habenula controls the voluntary ethanol intake, while damage of habenula in Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome escalates the voluntary ethanol intake. Chronic and excessive consumption of alcohol may facilitate the progression to Korsakoff's syndrome.
Amnesic effects	Dopamine enhances motivational declarative memory in young human adults, while dopaminergic antagonist impairs declarative memory recall in humans.	Joint damages only to both mammillary bodies and midline thalamus disconnecting habenula are sufficient to cause amnesia in humans.	Joint damages only to both mammillary bodies and midline thalamus disconnecting habenula are sufficient to cause amnesia in humans.

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Authors' Contributions

The sole one author responsible for all of the article.

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